

EXPLORING THE ECONOMIC POTENTIALS OF TOURISM IN SOUTHERN KADUNA, NIGERIA.

¹Yohanna, Shul-Nom Bako and ²Nnadi, Christian Uchenna

¹Department of History, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya. Nigeria.

²Department of Business Education, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya. Nigeria.

E-mail: shulnom710@gmail.com, uchennadiok@gmail.com

Phone Number: +2347068136232, +2348037528674

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Abstract: Tourism is an essential sector that is capable of changing the fortunes of a country or region economically and culturally. The underutilization of economic potentials of tourism in Southern Kaduna is largely hinged on insufficient investment in infrastructure such as transportation and hotels. Failure to address the infrastructural deficit can lead to loss of economic opportunities and limited community development. This study is anchored on the need to explore the economic potentials of tourism in Southern Kaduna area. The Southern Kaduna within the context of this study include; Jaba, Jema'a, Kaura, Kauru, Sanga, Zango-Kataf, Kachia and Kagarko local government areas constituting the Southern Kaduna Senatorial District of Kaduna State. Southern Kaduna is inhabited by diverse ethnic and linguistic groups belonging to the broader Niger-Congo linguistic family. The cardinal aim of this study is to proffer solutions to the underutilization of tourism potentials in Southern Kaduna. The specific objectives of this study include: To point out the major tourist sites in Southern Kaduna, to ascertain the nature of road network leading to tourist sites in Southern Kaduna, to unravel the economic prospects of tourism in Southern Kaduna and to assess the extent of government commitment in revamping tourism in Southern Kaduna. Qualitative research approach was used in conducting this research. Data for the study was obtained from both primary and secondary sources of information and subjected to a process of descriptive analysis. The sources of information for the study is a combination of the survey method with oral interviews and the library method. The survey method and oral interviews provided the primary sources of data, while the library approach provided the secondary sources of information used to analyze the study.

Keywords: Tourism Development, Economic Potentials, Infrastructure Deficit, Southern Kaduna, Community Development

Introduction

Tourism is an important sector in many countries around the world, contributing to economic growth, job creation, and cultural exchange. Tourism is a major source of revenue for a good number of countries, contributing to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth and creating jobs in various sectors such as hospitality, transportation and retail. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council, tourism accounted for 10.4% of global GDP in 2019.

(WTTC, 2024). while tourism brings economic benefits, it can have both positive and negative social impacts on local or host communities. On one hand, tourism can create employment opportunities, preserve cultural heritage and promote cross-cultural understanding. On the other hand, it can also lead to social inequality and loss of authenticity or value system in traditional practices thereby, threatening their cultural identity.

It is essential for stakeholders in the tourism sector, including governments and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), to synergize in order to ensure the emergence of responsible and inclusive development of tourism for the benefit of all, especially the host communities. By promoting sustainable practices, preserving cultural heritage and embracing innovation in Southern Kaduna, we can create a more resilient and vibrant tourism industry and attract people far and near which will in turn open room for economic growth and stability of the region in particular and the nation at large. The economic and cultural potential embedded in Nok town, located in Jaba LGA in the study area is enormous due to the place of Nok Culture or Nok Civilization in African history.

The Concept of Tourism

Tourism has always held appeal as a means of discovery, self-realization, self-consciousness, and, to a certain extent, escape. Certainly, tourists and their hosts throughout time have both been engaged in this form of self-reflection. Irrespective of the shifting landscape of global tourism, for some time, studying and writing about the history of tourism was an activity in which few scholars engaged, and even fewer considered the impact of tourism on host societies. (Cleveland, 2021).

When we think of tourism, we think primarily of people who are visiting a particular place for sightseeing, visiting friends and relatives, taking a vacation, and having a good time. They may spend their leisure time engaging in various sports, sunbathing, talking, singing, taking rides, touring, reading, or simply enjoying the environment. If we consider the subject further, we may include in our definition of tourism people who are participating in a convention, a business conference, or some other kind of business or professional activity, as well as those who are taking a study tour under an expert guide or doing some kind of scientific research or study. These visitors use all forms of transportation, from hiking in a wilderness park to flying in a jet to an exciting city.

Any attempt to define tourism and to describe its scope fully must consider the various groups that participate in and are affected by this industry. Thus, tourism may be defined as the processes, activities, and outcomes arising from the relationships and the interactions among tourists, tourism suppliers, host governments, host communities, and surrounding environments that are involved in the attracting and hosting of visitors. Tourism is a composite of activities, services, and industries that deliver a travel experience: transportation, accommodations, eating and drinking establishments, shops, entertainment, activity facilities, and other hospitality services available for individuals or groups that are traveling away from home. It encompasses all providers of visitor and visitor-related services. Tourism is the entire world industry of travel, hotels, transportation, and all other components that, including promotion, serve the needs and wants of travelers. Finally, tourism is the total of tourist expenditures within the borders of a nation or a political subdivision or a transportation-centered economic area of contiguous states or nations. This economic concept also considers the income multiplier of these tourist expenditures. (Goeldner & Richie, 2009).

The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines tourism as people “traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment” for leisure, business, or other purposes. For travel to qualify as tourism under this definition, it must last more than 24 hours and not last more than one year. Tourism industry plays a vital role in global economy. (Barten, 2024). According to World Travel and Tourism Council Economic Impact Report, in 2022, the Travel and Tourism sector contributed 7.6% to global GDP. Travel and tourism is also an

important source of employment. In 2024, the sector supported 357 million jobs globally, which is approximately 1 in 10 jobs. (WTTC, 2024).

Approximately 60 per cent of all of UNESCO's World Heritage Sites (natural and cultural) are located in developing nations, depending on precisely how these are defined. Some of the most spectacular remnants of ancient civilizations and contemporary colonial patrimony are located in developing regions. The Pyramids of Giza and Valley of the Kings (Egypt), Angkor Wat (Cambodia), Borobudur and Prambanan (Indonesia), the ancient city of Timbuktu (Mali), the Roman ruins of Palmyra (Syria), Great Zimbabwe Monument (Zimbabwe), Tikal (Guatemala), Lumbini, the birthplace of Buddha (Nepal), historic Istanbul (Turkey), and Dracula's Castle (Romania) are all examples of well-known and highly visible heritage places in the less developed world.

The New Seven Wonders of the World project was initiated in 2001 by a non-government body of volunteers to determine the modern world's most spectacular cultural wonders to correspond to those of the ancient world. The organization, New7Wonders, called for a global referendum to determine the seven wonders of the modern world. This hyped-up and highly visible campaign

resulted in the 2007 announcement (after apparently more than 100 million votes) of seven new wonders of the world, six of which are located in less-developed countries: Chichen Itza (Mexico), Christ Redeemer (Brazil), Great Wall of China (China), Taj Mahal (India), Petra (Jordan), and Macchu Pichu (Peru). The seventh is the Colosseum in Italy. (Timothy & Nyaupane, 2009).

Worthy of note is that Southern Kaduna has tourism potentials but underutilized due to neglect from both government and the private sector and the fulcrum of this study is to push for a paradigm shift.

Research Methodology

Qualitative research approach was used in conducting this research. Data for the study was obtained from both primary and secondary sources of information and subjected to a process of descriptive analysis. The sources of information for the study is a combination of the survey method with oral interviews and the library method. The survey method and oral interviews provided the primary sources of data, while the library approach provided the secondary sources of information used to analyze the study.

a. **Research Design:** Qualitative research design was explored in carrying out this research which involved the analysis of data obtained from the survey method as an approach which relied on public opinion or views about both the thematic and geographical scope under consideration. In this study, indigenous people's views were obtained through oral interviews.

b. **Study Area:** The study area includes the eight (8) local government areas (LGAs) which constitute the Southern Kaduna Senatorial District which is also known as Zone Three in the Kaduna State political spectrum. The local governments that constitute the study area are; Jaba, Jema'a, Kaura, Kauru, Sanga, Zango-Kataf, Kachia and Kagarko local government areas of Kaduna State.

Map of Kaduna State indicating the eight Local Governments that constitutes the study area.

Theoretical Framework

This work adopts the Destination Life Cycle Theory propounded by Richard W. Butler in 1980 in his seminal paper titled “The Concept of a Tourist Area Cycle of Evolution: Implications for Management of Resources.” The theory outlines a linear model describing the evolution of tourist destinations through six stages: Exploration, Involvement, Development, Consolidation, Stagnation, Rejuvenation or decline. (Butler, 1980) each stage represents different characteristics regarding visitor numbers, economic impact, and community involvement.

In the initial exploration stage, a destination is discovered by some adventurous travelers. These explorers often seek unique experiences away from mainstream tourism. At this point, Butler stated that the destination has limited facilities and infrastructure. The involvement stage witnesses increased tourism interest as local communities begin to recognize the potential economic benefits of tourism. Initial developments emerge, such as the construction of accommodations and transportation services.

Worth noting is that during the development stage, a marked increase in visitor numbers occurs, which stimulates more substantial investments in infrastructure and services. The tourism-related facilities become more commercialized, and marketing efforts are directed toward directing a broader audience. By this time, the destination may begin to experience economic benefits but also face challenges such as environmental degradation and cultural dilution. The consolidation stage marks a plateau of visitor numbers where the destination achieves a higher level of recognition but begins to show signs of strain. This stage often brings heightened competitions and pressures on local resources. Destinations often rely heavily on repeat visitors. In the stagnation stage, growth stagnates, and many aspects of the destination may suffer as quality declines and overcrowding becomes obvious.

Finally, in the rejuvenation or decline stage, a destination can undergo revitalization efforts to enhance its appeal and attract new visitors, or it may face decline if it cannot adapt to market changes. The theory underscores the importance of sustainable practices to maintain the viability of tourist destinations. One influential figure in advancing Butler's theory is J.F Brooker, who built upon the destination life cycle model in the 1990s by examining the importance of collaboration among stakeholders in fostering sustainable tourism. The emphasis on stakeholder engagement has greatly influenced modern tourism management practices. Brooker (1998). This work aligns with the content of the Butler's Destination Life Cycle Theory within the context of the study area. Butler's theory is being criticized for being deterministic but remains foundational.

Major Tourist Sites in Southern Kaduna

Tourism is a complex and multifaceted industry that engulfs various activities, experiences and services from different actors. The need to promote tourism as an economic tool for better service to the various host communities of tourist sites and the public cannot be overemphasized. This study is anchored on the need to explore the economic potentials of tourism in Southern Kaduna area. Ibrahim James in his book; 'Studies in the History, Politics and Cultures of Southern Kaduna Peoples Groups. James (1997); described the geo-political entity commonly referred to as "Southern Zaria" now Southern Kaduna as situated within the central high plains of Northern Nigeria. It is located between a longitude of 5° and 7° East. Southern Kaduna is inhabited by diverse ethnic and linguistic groups belonging to the broader Niger-Congo linguistic family (James, 2007).

The motivation for this study is borne out of the need to bring to bare the numerous opportunities imbedded in the nature's gift to Southern Kaduna and its potentials for socio-economic improvement of the region at large and the host communities in particular. The major tourist sites in Southern Kaduna in terms of natural and physical nature are:

i. **The Nok Museum and Nok Civilization:** Nok town is located in Jaba Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. Nok offers a glimpse into the initial discovery site and has a small Museum established by the National Commission for Museums and Monuments (NCMM) which houses few Nok Civilization artifacts and carry out educational services and guided tours. The museum and Nok general area are host to many tourists and academicians from within and outside Nigeria.

The civilization known as Nok Culture has been seen as a transitional culture between the Stone Age and the Iron Age in Nigeria because of the presence of a combination of stone and iron objects...Nok Culture existed between the 5th and 2nd Century B.C. It belonged to a people who had a lot of things in common and who had a well-organized economy. Nok Culture is important in Nigerian history because the people made iron tools and weapons. Apart from the iron-smelting furnaces and the terra-cotta sculptures of animals and human figurines found in the area, they also smelted tin because tin beads were found in some of the sites. Some people also made pottery. It has been suggested that Ife art appears to be an off-shoot of the Nok Culture because of the resemblance in the terracotta heads which they produced. (Eluwa, et al., 2009)

Explaining the value or importance of the famous Nok Culture, Eluwa further stated that some would even argue that many other cultures north and south of the River Niger developed from the Nok Culture but this is yet to be proved. Nok art has been described as geometric and rigid. It has been said that the Jaba (Ham people) who today live in the Nok area still use the hair styles found on the Nok terra-cotta heads. The Nok Culture is also important because it has helped to push back the antiquity of Nigerian history by showing that Nigerians produced and used iron tools and weapons as early as 500 B.C.

As important as the Nok Culture is, the major challenges facing the Nok community are infrastructural deficit, especially poor road network. The infrastructural deficit has been highlighted by Sedua Dwa as the biggest problem facing Nok museum and the entire Nok community. There is unavailability of pipe borne water and standard schools. The Nok historical sites have the capacity to generate revenue to the government and the locality if properly handled. (S. Dwa, personal communication, July 8th, 2025).

Plate 1. A collection of Nok terracotta head replica.

Plate 2. An ancient cave with barns in the village of Nok.

ii. **Kagoro Hills and Defunct North Central State Water Board Facility:** Kagoro is a town located in Kaura Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Nigeria. The area is rich in terms of geographical features with hills and valleys and spring water. “The Kagoro Water Treatment Plant is located in Kpak District of Kagoro

Chiefdom” (D. Isaiah, Personal Communication, August 2nd, 2025). The Kagoro Community hosts the defunct North Central State Water Board inaugurated by Colonel David Lasisi Bamigboye, the then Military Governor of Kwara State on 1st February, 1975. The Water Board in Kagoro supplies water to Kafanchan town and environs. However, the current condition of the Water Board/treatment plant is in a bad shape which requires urgent attention.

The Kagoro Hill has a settlement on top of the hill with farming, hunting and other endeavors occurring which attracts tourists. The Kagoro community is host to the famous Katagwan footprints and grave. The Kagoro people believe that Katagwan was a giant, great hunter and warrior who defended his people and aid people to cross the Dusai River when water overflows during the wet season. Another historical site is the Kajim swing bridge. Notably, the Kagoro Hill has multiple caves.

Plate 3: The defunct North Central State Water Board inaugurated by Colonel David Lasisi Bamigboye, the then Military Governor of Kwara State on 1st February, 1975.

iii. **Matsirga Waterfall:** The Matsirga/Attat waterfall is located about two kilometers away from Kafanchan popular ‘NEPA roundabout’. “the general area including the Madakiya axis is called Batadon by the locals.” (S. Kazzah, Personal Communication, August 1st, 2025). The waterfall derived its source from the Kagoro hill springs which cascade from four separate hollows of about 25 meters rock cliff which formed a large pool at its bottom. The Matsirga/Attat waterfall which is also known as ‘River Wonderful’ has a total height of 25 m (82 ft) and total width of 200 m (656 ft). My Guide Nigeria (2025, p.1) stated that

It is an area of outstanding natural beauty, which is both tranquil and breathtaking; if you are lucky, you will catch one of the mysterious rainbows that appear in the spray of the waterfalls. It is a bird-watchers’ paradise as several parrots and finches inhabit the nearby trees.

The waterfall provides a beautiful site to tourists or passersby and can attract more tourists from within and outside Nigeria when properly managed or harnessed by the local authorities. A good feeder road to the waterfall will make the tourist site more spectacular and easier to access.

Plate 4. *Matsirga Water Fall*

iv. Gurara Dam: Gurara Dam is located in Kachia and parts of Kagarko Local Government Areas of Kaduna State. “The project involves civil and ancillary works for the construction of the Gurara Dam, 52.5 m high and 3 km long at the crest with a reservoir of approximately 880 million m³ of water” (Webuild, 2025). The multi-purpose dam is aimed at meeting water needs of the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja), to generate electricity for Kaduna industrial zone and develop modern irrigation systems in the valley of the River Gurara and pave way for tourism potentials in the area. Worth noting is that Gurara River extends to about 360 km southwards from the dam, running just north of Jere town, then through Niger State and through the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja, to its confluence with River Niger in Kogi State. The Gurara Dam watershed area is bounded to the south by the FCT, to the west by Niger State, to the north by Kachia Local Government Area and to the east by Kagarko Local Government Area of Kaduna State. (Gams, 2025). With due diligence on the Gurara Dam project, it can be a tourist hub.

Plate 5. A section of the Gurara Dam

v. **Nimbia Forest Reserve:** The Nimbia Forest Reserve is located in Jema'a Local Government of Kaduna State seventy kilometers South East of Jos along Jos-Kafanchan road. "Nimbia Forest Reserve covers an area of about 2,282.4 hectares. It is long and narrow in shape, bounded on the South by Gimi River and on the North by the Lioc Stream (Obidike, 2011). The natural vegetation was cleared in 1957 by the then Jema'a Native Authority and replaced with mainly teak (*Tectona grandis*) and few *gmelinas arboreas* stands. The first trial plantation of teak started in 1957, and between 1958 and 1966, 98.42 hectares were planted with teak. The planting continued at intervals over the years bringing it to its current state.

Plate 6: Nimbia Forest Reserve in Jema'a Local Government, Kaduna State.

Major Cultural Festivals in Southern Kaduna

There are many cultural festivals in Southern Kaduna aside the Christian and Islam religious festivities celebrated by Christians and Muslims during Sallah, Christmas and Easter celebrations. The major cultural festivals in the study area are the Southern Kaduna Festival (SKFEST), Afan Cultural Festival and Tuk-Ham Cultural Festival.

Southern Kaduna Festival (SKFEST): The Southern Kaduna Festival popularly known as SKFEST was conceived in the year 2023 to revitalize the cultural heritage of the Southern Kaduna peoples and celebrate their unity in diversity which showcasing the people's rich cultural heritage. According to Leadership News (2024) the three-day event includes an opening ceremony, exhibition of traditional arts, cuisine fair, beauty pageant and fashion show, live music concerts, colloquium, and sports such as football tournament, marathon race, traditional wrestling, archery and boxing (danbe). The festival was design to foster cross-cultural and intergenerational engagement between the young and the older generations of Southern Kaduna indigenes. The Southern Kaduna Festival occurs in December.

The Afan Cultural Festival: The Afan Cultural Festival of the Kagoro people is one of the most popular cultural festival in Southern Kaduna and beyond which attracts tourists from within and outside the shores of Nigeria.

The word Afan means "mountain" or "hill" in the Gworok language, and it is from these majestic hills that the festival derives its name. The Gworok Hills-soaring at an altitude of over 1,200 meters-are not only scenic but deeply spiritual...in ancient times, the Agworok people lived atop these hills, retreating into caves and heights for safety. British colonial forces eventually displaced them to the base of the mountains, but some communities still remain on the highlands... originally celebrated in April, the date of the festival was moved to January 1st during the reign of HRN (Dr.) Gwamna Awan, the first Christian Chief of Kagoro, in 1946. His leadership marked a transition from the festival's traditional pagan rites to a more inclusive cultural celebration aligned with Christian values and the Gregorian calendar. (NICO, 2020).

Worth noting is that the Afan festival marked the end of a farming season and beginning of hunting in the bush and hills within the Kagoro area and beyond.

The Tuk Ham Cultural Festival: Tuk Ham means "Ham Celebration" The Tuk Ham Cultural Festival is an annual cultural event which is celebrated during Easter period (April) where Ham sons and daughters in Ribí Ham (Hamland) and beyond come together to celebrate through cultural practices/processions and pray for a good farming season ahead. The festival takes place in Kwain (Kwoi), the capital of Jaba Local Government Area of Kaduna State.

The perception of the Tuk Ham Movement as conceived by M. Kure Manchaik, M. Musa Gaiya, M. Musa Haruna, M. Yaki Jatau, M. Adamu Maikori, M. Agwai Anji and Alhaji Musa Gidan Mana was to secure the restoration of Ham unity and solidarity to its pre-1903 division of Hamland by the British Colonial Administration. The Tuk Ham Cultural Festival was used merely as a vehicle and an instrument for attaining this supreme objective.... The first Tuk Ham Festival occurred from the 4-6 April, 1980 at Kwoi. Kpop Ham Danladi Gyet Maude addressed the gathering by giving a brief history of the Ham people and the reasons for inaugurating the Festival. The reasons advanced ranged from the political objective of achieving Ham unity through the economic aspirations of the rapid development of Ribí-Ham to the cultural objectives of reviving the Ham Cultural Heritage. This experimental Tuk Ham Cultural Festival went without any hitch or problem. (James, 1997)

James' account above pictured the political and cultural objectives of the Tuk-Ham Cultural Festival worth noting is that the celebration of Tuk Ham, ab initio, serves two purposes: first, to thank God for the past farming season. Secondly, to pray for a favorable farming season ahead. There are activities such as symposium, beauty pageant to pick Tir Ham from the various contestants, musical concerts, free medical outreach and competition. The final

day of the Tuk Ham Festival brings together people from Hamland and beyond where cultural displays and art exhibition takes center stage and is often spiced with speeches by dignitaries.

“The Tuk-Ham Festival is a haven of cultural delights for those interested in music, food, and crafts.” Traditional Ham folk songs, accompanied by drumming and flute music, create a lively ambience throughout the event.” (Rexclarke, 2025). The Tuk Ham Cultural Festival market stands gives people the opportunity to buy handmade jewelry, leather materials, woven fabrics, local farm tools, Nok terracotta sculptures and other items of interest to visitors.

A look into the Southern Kaduna Festival (SKFEST), the Afan Festival, the Tuk Ham Cultural Festival, Nok Museum/Nok Civilization, Kagoro Hills and Defunct North Central State Water Board Facility and the Matsirga waterfall shows how the cultural festivals and the tourism sites are in line with Richard Butler’s Destination Life Cycle Theory adopted for this work which provides a framework for understanding the evolution of tourist destinations overtime.

Economic Potentials of Tourism in Southern Kaduna

The study area has enormous economic potentials but they are grossly underutilized overtime. The ancient Nok settlement in Jaba Local Government Area of Kaduna State has the historical fulcrum to attract revenue to both the host community and the government. The Southern Kaduna Festival (SKFEST) is beyond mere display of cultural extravaganza. It is also geared toward drawing the attention of investors due to the enormous rich resources and cultural heritage sites in Southern Kaduna as a whole.

Southern Kaduna has a conducive environment and tourist sites capable of contributing to its economic growth. The tourism sector can provide platforms to create job opportunities (hospitality, travel agencies, tour operations and cultural sites management) infrastructural development, foreign exchange earnings and community development of the host communities of tourism sites. Worth noting is that:

In 2023, Nigeria recorded 1.2 million international visitors and saw domestic tourism trips increase by 20% to three million, within a potential market of 200 million travelers. The tourism sector contributed 3.65% (\$17.3 billion) to Nigeria’s GDP in 2022 and employed 1.91 million people. The country’s tourism industry is rich in cultural attractions. Including over 1,000 annual festivals and two UNESCO World Heritage Sites. Though challenges such as infrastructure and security persist. (Statista, 2024)

Tourism in the study area when properly harnessed, can serve as a means of promoting cultural heritage and environmental conservation. Southern Kaduna is home to different ethnic nationalities and traditions, which provides shades of cultural attractions. Festivals, arts, and crafts can attract tourists within and outside Nigeria, thereby, generating income to the local communities and other investors.

Factors Affecting Tourism Potentials in Southern Kaduna

Despite the immense potentials for tourism in Southern Kaduna, several factors are hindering the full realization of these potentials (rich cultural heritage, diverse landscape, good weather and variety of attractions). The major factor affecting tourism potential in Southern Kaduna and even Nigeria as a whole is inadequate infrastructure. There is poor road network and public transportation systems are poor in most cases which makes it difficult for tourists to travel across Southern Kaduna and visit different attractions. The Nok village which is located in Jaba Local Government in Southern Kaduna has a very poor road leading to the Nok Museum and other historic sites in the Nok general area.

Another factor that hinders tourism potential in Southern Kaduna is insecurity. The area has witnessed security challenges in several locations recently including terrorism, kidnaping and banditry which affects the influx of

visitors to the study area. No tourist will feel comfortable visiting a crisis prone area. The number of security personnel in Nigeria as a whole is inadequate and the study area is not immune from the inadequate security personnel. Where local vigilante exists, they are poorly motivated and lack proper training and ammunition to use in securing the area.

Lack of investment in the tourism sites in the study area is another glaring barrier to the growth of tourism. Many tourist facilities in Southern Kaduna are not in good shape and need renovation. Without adequate investment, it is difficult to improve the quality of attractions, accommodation and services available to tourists. Most of the hotels in the area do not meet international standards and may not appeal to foreign visitors.

Recommendations

In order to find a lasting solution to the underutilization of the economic potentials of tourism in Southern Kaduna, the following recommendations are preferred:

- i. Provision of infrastructure: Infrastructural facilities, especially construction of good roads, hospitals, telecommunication and adequate water supply by both government and the private sector.
- ii. The need to strengthen security: Security in Southern Kaduna should be adequately strengthened. The rising case of kidnapping, banditry and activities of terrorists who attack and decimate some communities is a bitter experience that is capable of scaring investors and tourists to the area. Local vigilante groups should be trained and motivated in order to compliment the regular security architecture in Southern Kaduna.
- iii. Proper investment: The lack of investment in tourism is causing a lot of setback to tourism in the study area. Both the government and the private sector should invest in tourism to utilize the study area's tourism potential.
- iv. Creating awareness: there is a need to create awareness on the need to tap into the tourism potentials of Southern Kaduna and galvanize support from relevant stakeholders through both print and electronic media and local communication channels.
- v. Creating synergy with Tourism Boards and National Commission for Museums and Monuments: There should be synergy between the statutory relevant agencies and stakeholders in Southern Kaduna in order to revamp the tourism sector.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the economic potentials of tourism in Southern Kaduna are immense. By taking advantage of its rich cultural heritage, natural resources, and the pressing need for infrastructure development, Southern Kaduna can transform its tourism sector into a powerful engine for economic advancement. With strategic blueprint for action and investment, Southern Kaduna can harness tourism to rejuvenate its economic growth which will to a large extent improve the livelihood of Southern Kaduna people and Nigeria at large.

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